

New data on the ground beetles (Coleoptera: Carabidae) of Serbia

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Abstract. The study reports 157 species of Carabidae from Serbia. Twenty species, five subgenera, two genera and one tribe are first reported for Serbia. Nine species are first recorded with exact data for the country, and other seven species – for a second time. Totally, 111 species are cited from the Vojvodina Province, 108 of them from the Fruška Gora Mt. as 56 species are first cited for the Vojvodina Province, and other 13 are first recorded for it with exact data.

Key words: Coleoptera, Carabidae, Serbia, Palaearctic region, faunistics, new records.

Introduction

Recently, ČURČIĆ et al. (2007) took stock of the family Carabidae (excl. Cicindelinae) of Serbia. As a result the fauna of country seems well-studied as 576 species and 167 subspecies from 107 genera have been listed (ibid.). But, as the authors noted (ibid.), some areas as Vojvodina and the southeastern part of the country remain still inadequately studied. On the other hand, after the recent separation of Kosovo, the number of taxa inhabiting Serbia decreased on account of both local endemic taxa and such hitherto recorded only from the former Kosovo Province.

This article reports data about 157 species from the collections of several European museums. Twenty of the species are first established for Serbia, and a great deal of other species is first recorded for the Vojvodina Province.

Material and methods

The material in seven European museums has been investigated. Altogether 1887 specimens of 157 species originating from Serbia have been revised. It is worth noting that among the historical collections that of G. Paganetti-Hummeler (1871 – 1949) preserved in MIZ and NMW is of importance for the fauna of the Vojvodina Province of Serbia.

The term “Central Serbia” (= Ужа Србија or Uža Srbija, in Serbian) is used for the region of Central Serbia, the main territory of present Serbia, and the term “Vojvodina Province” is used for the northern part of the country having territorial autonomy (Fig. 1).

Abbreviations used:

BMNH: Natural History Museum, London, United Kingdom

HNHM: Hungarian Natural History Museum, Budapest, Hungary

MNHN: Muséum National d'Histoire Naturelle, Paris, France

MIZ: Museum and Institute of Zoology, Polish Academy of Sciences, Warszawa, Poland

NMW: Naturhistorisches Museum Wien, Vienna, Austria

MNHUB: Museum für Naturkunde der Humboldt Universität zu Berlin, Berlin, Germany

ZMAN: Zoologisch Museum Amsterdam, Nederland

s. – specimen/s; m. – male/s; f. – female/s

Fig. 1. Administrative map of Serbia. The black rectangle indicates the position of the Fruška Gora Mt.

List of species

***Leistus (Leistus) ferrugineus* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

Material examined: “Fruška Gora”, 4 s. (MIZ).

Notes. Species already noted for Vojvodina without exact data (ĆURČIĆ et al., 2007: 293). First exact record from the Vojvodina Province.

***Notiophilus biguttatus* (Fabricius, 1779)**

Material examined: “Fruška Gora Sirmien.”, 27 s. (MIZ).

Notes. First record from the Vojvodina Province.

***Notiophilus palustris* (Duftschmid, 1812)**

Material examined: “Fruška Gora Sirmien.”, 1 s. (MIZ).

Notes. Species already noted for Vojvodina without exact data (ĆURČIĆ et al., 2007: 302). First exact record from the Vojvodina Province.

***Elaphrus (Elaphroterus) aureus* P.W.J. Müller, 1821**

Material examined: “Jugoslavia Nis. 1957 V.”, / “legit dr. Lency”, 3 s. (HNHM); “Fruška Gora Sirmien.”, 23 s. (MIZ).

Notes. First record from the Vojvodina Province.

***Aptinus (Aptinus) bombardata* Illiger, 1800**

Material examined: “Fruška Gora Sirmien.”, 61 s. (MIZ).

Notes. Species already reported from the Fruška Gora Mt. (ĆURČIĆ et al., 2007: 80).

***Brachinus (Brachinus) elegans* Chaudoir, 1842 [= *ganglbaueri* Apfelbeck, 1904]**

Material examined: "Bela Palanka Serbia" / "Coll. Apfelbeck", 1 syntype of *Brachinus ganglbaueri* Apfelbeck, 1904 (HNHM).

***Brachinus (Brachinus) psophia* Audinet-Serville, 1821**

Material examined: "Fruska Gora", 1 s. (MIZ); "Fruška Gora Syrmien", 3 s. (MIZ).

Notes. First record from the Vojvodina Province.

***Brachinus (Brachinus) crepitans* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

Material examined: "Fruska Gora", 9 s. (MIZ); "Fruška Gora Syrmien", 14 s. (MIZ).

Notes. Species already noted from the Fruška Gora Mt. (ĆURČIĆ et al., 2007: 81).

***Clivina collaris* (Herbst, 1784)**

Material examined: "Fruska Gora", 4 s. (MIZ); "Fruška Gora Syrmien", 1 s. (MIZ).

Notes. First record from the Vojvodina Province.

***Clivina fossor* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

Material examined: "Fruska Gora", 1 s. (MIZ); "Fruška Gora Syrmien.", 2 s. (MIZ).

Notes. ĆURČIĆ et al. (2007: 304) have already noted it for the Vojvodina Province.

***Clivina laevifrons* Chaudoir, 1842**

Material examined: "Serbien Paracin 1918 Dr. Maertens", 2 s. (MNHUB).

***Dyschirius (Dyschiriodes) aeneus* (Dejean, 1825)**

Material examined: "Fruska Gora", 4 s. (MIZ).

Notes. First record from the Vojvodina Province.

***Dyschirius (Dyschiriodes) chalybaeus* Putzeys, 1846**

Material examined: "Dr. Hensch Ruma Slav.", 1 s. (MNHUB).

Notes. First record from the Vojvodina Province. The Balkan populations of species belong to ssp. *gibbifrons* Apfelbeck, 1899.

***Dyschirius (Dyschiriodes) laeviusculus* Putzeys, 1846**

Material examined: "Tschatschak Serbia", 1 s. (MIZ).

***Dyschirius (Eudyschirius) globosus* (Herbst, 1784)**

Material examined: "Fruska Gora", 5 s. (MIZ).

Notes. First exact data for Vojvodina. Recently, this species was cited for Vojvodina without exact data (ĆURČIĆ et al., 2007: 308).

***Dyschirius (Paradyschirius) parallelus* Motschulsky, 1844**

Material examined: "Serbia, Salac", 2 s. (HNHM).

Notes. The Balkan populations of species belong to ssp. *ruficornis* Putzeys, 1846.

***Dicropterus brevipennis* (J. Frivaldszky, 1879)**

Material examined: "Serbia Merkl, 1885", 2 **syntypes** (1 m., 1 f.) of *Scotodipnus serbicus* Ganglbauer (HNHM).

Notes. The Serbian population of species belongs to ssp. *serbicus* (Ganglbauer, 1900).

***Asaphidion flavipes* (Linnaeus, 1761)**

Material examined: "Fruska Gora", 16 s. (MIZ); "Fruška Gora Sarmien.", 3 s. (MIZ).

Notes. ČURČIĆ et al. (2007: 312) have mentioned it for Fruška Gora Mt.

***Asaphidion nebulosum* (P. Rossi, 1792)**

Material examined: "Svrligiska planina Serbie orientale", 1 s. (NMW).

Notes. The Balkan populations of species belong to ssp. *balcanicum* Netolitzky, 1918.

***Asaphidion pallipes* (Duftschmid, 1812)**

Material examined: "Fruska Gora", 2 s. (MIZ); "Fruška Gora Sarmien.", 2 s. (MIZ).

Notes. Species already cited for the Fruška Gora Mt. (ČURČIĆ et al., 2007: 313).

***Bembidion (Bembidion) quadrimaculatum* (Linnaeus, 1761)**

Material examined: "Fruška Gora Sarmien.", 16 s. (MIZ); "Jugoslavia Arandjelovac 20.VII-2.VIII '35 H. J. Mac Gillavry", 1 s. (ZMAN).

Notes. ČURČIĆ et al. (2007: 313) have noted it for the Vojvodina Province (Deliblato Sands).

***Bembidion (Bembidionetolitzkya) concoeruleum* Netolitzky, 1943**

Material examined: "Serbien Paracin 1918 Dr. Maertens", 1 m. (MNHUB); "Jugoslavia Nis, 1957.III." / "legit Dr. Lenczy", 1 f. (HNHM).

Notes. New species for Serbia. *B. concoeruleum* has been cited for the former Kosovo Province (ČURČIĆ et al., 2007: 314, as *B. coeruleum* Audinet-Serville, 1821). The previous data on *B. coeruleum* from the Balkan Peninsula concern *B. concoeruleum* (BONAVITA & VIGNA TAGLIANTI, 1993).

***Bembidion (Bembidionetolitzkya) geniculatum* Heer, 1837**

Material examined: "Fruška Gora Sarmien.", 2 m., 2 f. (MIZ).

Notes. ČURČIĆ et al. (2007: 314) have already noted it for the Vojvodina Province (Vršac).

***Bembidion (Bembidionetolitzkya) tibiale* (Duftschmid, 1812)**

Material examined: "Fruška Gora Sarmien.", 4 m., 5 f. (MIZ).

Notes. ČURČIĆ et al. (2007: 315) have listed it for the Fruška Gora Mt.

***Bembidion (Bembidionetolitzkya) varicolor* (Fabricius, 1803)**

Material examined: "Fruška Gora Sarmien.", 12 s. (MIZ).

Notes. First record from the Vojvodina Province.

***Bembidion (Bracteon) litorale* (Olivier, 1790)**

Material examined: "Jugoslavia Nis. 1957 V." / "legit dr. Lenczy", 1 f. (HNHM).

Notes. Species recorded from Niš (MATITS, 1922: 14).

***Bembidion (Chlorodium) pygmaeum* (Fabricius, 1792)**

Material examined: "Serb. Hlf. Požarevac", 1 s. (NMW).

***Bembidion (Chlorodium) splendidum* Sturm, 1825**

Material examined: "Serb. Hlf. Požarevac", 1 s. (HNHM).

Notes. Species has already been cited from Požarevac (ČURČIĆ et al., 2007: 317).

***Bembidion (Diplocampa) assimile* Gyllenhal, 1810**

Material examined: "Fruška Gora Syrmien.", 1 s. (MIZ); "Jugoslavia Arandjelovac 20.VII-2.VIII '35 H. J. Mac Gillavry", 2 s. (ZMAN).

Notes. ČURČIĆ et al. (2007: 317) have cited it for Vojvodina (Ruma; Deliblato Sands).

***Bembidion (Emphanes) latiplaga* Chaudoir, 1850**

Material examined: "Serb. Hlf. Požarevac", 1 s. (NMW).

Notes. Species already cited from Požarevac (ČURČIĆ et al., 2007: 318).

***Bembidion (Eupetedromus) dentellum* (Thunberg, 1787)**

Material examined: At least 150 s. labeled "Fruska Gora" or "Fruška Gora Syrmien." (MIZ).

Notes. ČURČIĆ et al. (2007: 317) have noted it for Vojvodina (Kupinski Kut; Deliblato Sands).

***Bembidion (Metallina) lampros* (Herbst, 1784)**

Material examined: "Fruška Gora Syrmien.", 37 s. (MIZ).

Notes. Species already cited from Fruška Gora Mt. (ČURČIĆ et al., 2007: 322).

***Bembidion (Metallina) properans* (Stephens, 1828)**

Material examined: "Fruška Gora Syrmien.", 16 s. (MIZ).

Notes. ČURČIĆ et al. (2007: 322) have listed it for Vojvodina (Srbobran; Novi Sad).

***Bembidion (Microserrullula) quadricolle* (Motschulsky, 1844)**

Material examined: "Serb. Hlf. Požarevac", 1 s. (NMW).

Notes. Species known only from Požarevac (ČURČIĆ et al., 2007: 323).

***Bembidion (Notaphus) semipunctatum* (Donovan, 1806)**

Material examined: "Fruška Gora Syrmien.", 5 s. (MIZ); "Jugoslavia Arandjelovac 20.VII-2.VIII '35 H. J. Mac Gillavry", 1 s. (ZMAN).

Notes. ČURČIĆ et al. (2007: 324) have noted it for Vojvodina (Deliblato Sands).

***Bembidion (Ocydromus) decorum* (Zenker in Panzer, 1799)**

Material examined: "Fruška Gora Syrmien.", 2 s. (MIZ).

Notes. First record from the Vojvodina Province.

***Bembidion (Peryphanes) brunnicorne* Dejean, 1831**

Material examined: "Fruška Gora Syrmien.", 2 s. (MIZ); "Jugoslavia Arandjelovac 20.VII-2.VIII '35 H. J. Mac Gillavry", 2 s. (ZMAN).

Notes. First record from the Vojvodina Province.

***Bembidion (Trepanes) articulatum* (Panzer, 1796)**

Material examined: "Fruška Gora Syrmien.", 8 s. (MIZ).

Notes. First record from the Vojvodina Province.

***Sinechostictus (Pseudolimnaeum) doderoi* (Ganglbauer, 1891)**

Material examined: "Fruška Gora Syrmien Er. Tippman", 1 s. (NMW).

Notes. First record from the Vojvodina Province and second one from Serbia.

***Sinechostictus (Sinechostictus) millerianus* (Heyden, 1883)**

Material examined: “Fruška Gora Syrmien.”, 3 s. (MIZ).

Notes. First record from the Vojvodina Province. Species was until recently known only from Majdanpek and the Kopaonik Mt. (ĆURČIĆ et al., 2007: 335, as *Bembidion millerianum*).

***Sinechostictus (Sinechostictus) tarsicus* (Peyron, 1858)**

Material examined: “Tschatschak Serbia”, 1 s. (MIZ).

Notes. Species cited from Čačak (ĆURČIĆ et al., 2007: 334, as *Bembidion elongatum* Dejean, 1831).

***Tachyta (Tachyta) nana* (Gyllenhal, 1810)**

Material examined: “Fruska Gora”, 8 s. (MIZ); “Fruška Gora Syrmien.”, 10 s. (MIZ).

Notes. First record from the Vojvodina Province.

***Tachyura (Tachyura) diabrachys* (Kolenati, 1845)**

Material examined: “Serbia”, 1 s. (MNHUB); “Priboj”, 1 s. (HNHM).

Notes. New species for Serbia.

***Duvalius (Duvalius) sturanyi* (Apfelbeck, 1904)**

Material examined: “Bobita pl. Serb. 1000 m Nonvill. 9.4.1980”, 1 f. (HNHM).

Notes. Species already reported for Bobija Mt. (ĆURČIĆ et al., 2007: 342, as *Balkanoduvalius sturanyi*).

***Duvalius (Paraduvalius) stankovitchi* (Jeannel, 1924)**

Material examined: 4 s. (incl. 1 **syntype**) (NMW).

Notes. The material studied refers to ssp. *georgievitchi* (Jeannel, 1924).

***Pheggomisetes globiceps* Buresch, 1925**

Material examined: “Odžina rupa Odorovci” / “Serbia or. E. Pterner”, 2 s. (HNHM).

Notes. The material studied refers to ssp. *ilandjjevi* V.B. Guéorguiev, 1964.

***Pheggomisetes ninae* S.B. Ćurčić, Schönmann, Brajković, B.P.M. Ćurčić & Tomić, 2004**

Material examined: 1 m. **holotype** and 2 **paratypes** (NMW).

***Trechus (Trechus) cardioderus* Putzeys, 1870**

Material examined: “Fruska Gora”, 6 s. (NMW).

Notes. Species reported for Vojvodina from the area of Banat (ĆURČIĆ et al., 2007: 353).

***Trechus (Trechus) constrictus* Schaum, 1860**

Material examined: “Fruska Gora”, 1 m., 1 f. (MIZ); “Fruška Gora Syrmien”, 2 f. (MIZ).

Notes. New species for Serbia. The aedeagus of one male has been studied (Figs. 2-3) and compared to that depicted by JEANNEL (1927: 387, Fig. 949). The new locality is interesting since it extends the known range of the species further in the east and adds new data on the species' vertical distribution.

***Trechus (Trechus) limacodes* Dejean, 1831**

Material examined: “Fruska Gora”, 2 m., 1 f. (MIZ); “Fruška Gora Syrmien”, 1 f. (MIZ).

Notes. New species for Serbia. The genitalia have not been studied due to absence of

Fig. 2-3. Median lobe of aedeagus of *Trechus constrictus* Schaum (male from Fruška Gora Mt.): Fig. 2: lateral view; Fig. 3: dorsal view

sclerotised structures, and the series is thus provisionally referred to ssp. *jucundus* Csiki, 1912. The new data extend the known range of the species further in the east.

***Trechus (Trechus) priapus* K. Daniel, 1902**

Material examined: "Reiser 1899 Kopaonik" / "coll. Reitter", 4 syntypes (HNHM).

Notes. The population from Kopaonik Mt. forms endemic ssp. *serbicus* Apfelbeck, 1902.

***Trechus (Trechus) rotundipennis* (Duftschmid, 1812)**

Material examined: "Fruska Gora", 3 m., 1 f. (MIZ).

Notes. New species for Serbia. The aedeagus of one male has been studied (Fig. 4) and compared with that shown by JEANNEL (1927: 430, Fig. 1031). WINKLER (1936) has distinguished three races, and the series from Fruška Gora is thus referred to ssp. *cordicollis* Winkler, 1936. The new data extend the range of the species further in the east.

Fig. 4. Median lobe of aedeagus of *Trechus rotundipennis* (Duftschmid), lateral view (male from Fruška Gora Mt.)

***Callistus lunatus* (Fabricius, 1775)**

Material examined: "Fruska Gora", 11 s. (MIZ).

Notes. ĆURČIĆ et al. (2007: 149) have listed it for Vojvodina (Morović; Kumane).

***Chlaenius (Chlaeniellus) nigricornis* (Fabricius, 1787)**

Material examined: "Fruska Gora", 5 s. (MIZ); "Fruška Gora Syrmien.", 16 s. (MIZ).

Notes. ĆURČIĆ et al. (2007: 150) have cited it from the Vojvodina Province (Kumane).

***Chlaenius (Chlaeniellus) olivieri* Crotch, 1871 [= *variegates* (Geoffroy, 1785)]**

Material examined: "Serbien Paracin 1918 Dr. Maertens", 2 s. (MNHUB).

Notes. Second record from Serbia. Until recently, this species was known only from Dubravica (MATITS, 1922: 37, as *C. variegatus*).

***Chlaenius (Chlaenites) spoliatus* (P. Rossi, 1792)**

Material examined: "Fruska Gora", 2 s. (MIZ); "Fruška Gora Syrmien.", 2 s. (MIZ).

Notes. First record from the Vojvodina Province.

***Chlaenius (Chlaenius) festivus* (Panzer, 1796)**

Material examined: 45 s. from localities "Fruska Gora", "Fruska Gora Syrmien", and "Fruška Gora Syrmien." (MIZ).

Notes. First record from the Vojvodina Province.

***Chlaenius (Epomis) dejeanii* (Dejean, 1831)**

Material examined: "Serbien Paracin 1918 Dr. Maertens", 2 s. (MNHUB); "Avala b. Beograd leg. Bischoff 1930", 11 s. (NMW; MNHUB); "Košutnjak b. Beograd leg. Bischoff 1930", 1 s. (NMW); "Beograd Kalemegdan" / "Scheibel 7.X.31", 4 s. (MNHUB).

***Drypta (Drypta) dentata* (P. Rossi, 1790)**

Material examined: 13 s. labeled: "Fruska Gora", "Fruska Gora Syrmien", and "Fruška Gora Syrmien." (MIZ).

Notes. First record from the Vojvodina Province.

***Anisodactylus (Pseudanisodactylus) signatus* (Panzer, 1796)**

Material examined: "Serb. Hlf. Požarevac", 1 s. (HNHM).

Notes. Species recorded from Požarevac (ĆURČIĆ et al., 2007: 156).

***Diachromus germanus* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

Material examined: "Fruška Gora Syrmien.", 2 s. (MIZ).

Notes. First record from the Vojvodina Province.

***Dixus clypeatus* (P. Rossi, 1790)**

Material examined: "Fruška Gora Syrmien.", 1 s. (MIZ).

Notes. ĆURČIĆ et al. (2007: 157) have reported it for Vojvodina (Kumane; Zrenjanin).

***Harpalus (Cryptophonus) tenebrosus* Dejean, 1829**

Material examined: "Fruška Gora Syrmien.", 1 s. (MIZ).

Notes. Until recently, this species was known only from Majdanpek (ĆURČIĆ et al., 2007: 159). Second record from Serbia and first one from the Vojvodina Province.

***Harpalus (Harpalus) atratus* Latreille, 1804**

Material examined: "Fruska Gora Syrmien", 2 s. (MIZ); "Fruška Gora Syrmien.", 3 s. (MIZ).

Notes. First record from the Vojvodina Province.

***Harpalus (Harpalus) caspius* (Steven, 1806)**

Material examined: "Fruska Gora", 1 m., 2 f. (MIZ); "Fruska Gora Syrmien", 1 s. (MIZ); "Fruška Gora Syrmien.", 1 s. (MIZ).

Notes. ĆURČIĆ et al. (2007: 162) have listed this species for Serbia without exact locality. First exact data for Serbia and first record from the Vojvodina Province.

***Harpalus (Harpalus) cupreus* Dejean, 1829**

Material examined: "Fruska Gora Syrmien", 1 s. (MIZ).

Notes. Species already cited from the Fruška Gora Mt. (ĆURČIĆ et al., 2007: 163). The Balkan populations of species belong to ssp. *fastuosus* Faldermann, 1836.

***Harpalus (Harpalus) froelichii* Sturm, 1818**

Material examined: "Fruška Gora Syrmien.", 1 f. (MIZ).

Notes. Species already cited from the Fruška Gora Mt. (ĆURČIĆ et al., 2007: 166).

***Harpalus (Harpalus) honestus* (Duftschmid, 1812)**

Material examined: "Fruška Gora Syrmien.", 4 s. (MIZ).

Notes. First record from the Vojvodina Province.

***Harpalus (Harpalus) hospes* Sturm, 1818**

Material examined: "Sikora Serbien 1883.XI.", 1 s. (NMW); "Jugoslavia Nis 1957.IV" / "legit dr. Lenczy", 12 s. (HNHM).

Notes. Species already noted from the vicinity of Niš (ĆURČIĆ et al., 2007: 168).

***Harpalus (Harpalus) oblitus* Dejean, 1829**

Material examined: "Jamena a. Save leg. Bischoff 1930", 1 s. (MNHUB).

Notes. First record from the Vojvodina Province. The specimen bears a second label which erroneously indicates it as coming from Albania.

***Harpalus (Harpalus) servus* (Duftschmid, 1812)**

Material examined: "Fruska Gora", 1 f. (MIZ).

Notes. Until recently, this species was known only from Deliblato Sands, the Vojvodina Province (ĆURČIĆ et al., 2007: 174). Second record for Serbia.

***Harpalus (Harpalus) subcylindricus* Dejean, 1829**

Material examined: "Jugoslavia Nis, 1957 IV." / "legit dr. Lenczy", 2 s. (HNHM).

Notes. Until recently, this species was known only from the Kopaonik Mt. (ĆURČIĆ et al., 2007: 175). Second record for Serbia.

***Harpalus (Harpalus) taciturnus* Dejean, 1829**

Material examined: "Jugoslavia Nis, 1957.IV" / "legit. dr. Lenczy", 1 s. (HNHM).

Notes. New species for Serbia.

***Harpalus (Harpalus) tardus* (Panzer, 1796)**

Material examined: “Fruska Gora”, 3 s. (MIZ); “Fruška Gora Syrmien.”, 4 s. (MIZ).
Notes. Species noted for the Vojvodina Province (ĆURČIĆ et al., 2007: 176).

***Harpalus (Pseudophonus) calceatus* (Duftschmid, 1812)**

Material examined: “Fruska Gora”, 2 s. (MIZ); “Fruška Gora Syrmien.”, 1 s. (MIZ).
Notes. Species cited for the Vojvodina Province (ĆURČIĆ et al., 2007: 177).

***Harpalus (Semiophonus) signaticornis* (Duftschmid, 1812)**

Material examined: “Jugoslavia Nis 1957.IV” / “legit dr. Lenczy”, 1 s. (HNHM).
Notes. Species recorded from Niš (ĆURČIĆ et al., 2007: 180).

***Ophonus (Hesperophonus) cribricollis* (Dejean, 1829)**

Material examined: “Fruška Gora Syrmien.”, 1 s. (MIZ).
Notes. ĆURČIĆ et al. (2007: 181) have cited it for Vojvodina (Bečej; Zrenjanin).

***Ophonus (Metophonus) brevicollis* (Audinet-Serville, 1821)**

Material examined: “Fruska Gora”, 2 s. (MIZ); “Fruška Gora Syrmien.”, 4 s. (MIZ).
Notes. New species for Serbia.

***Ophonus (Metophonus) cordatus* (Duftschmid, 1812)**

Material examined: “Serb. Hlf. Ak-Palanka”, 1 s. (HNHM); “Jugoslavia Nis, 1957.IV” / “legit dr. Lenczy”, 1 s. (HNHM).
Notes. Species already cited from Bela Palanka (= Ak Palanka) (ĆURČIĆ et al., 2007: 182).

***Ophonus (Metophonus) puncticeps* Stephens, 1828**

Material examined: “Serbia Vranja” / “Horváth Sept. 1902”, 1 s. (HNHM); “Jugoslavia Arandjelovac 20.VII-2.VIII '35 H. J. Mac Gillavry”, 9 s. (ZMAN).
Notes. First exact record for Serbia.

***Ophonus (Metophonus) rupicola* (Sturm, 1818)**

Material examined: “Fruska Gora”, 1 s. (MIZ).
Notes. ĆURČIĆ et al. (2007: 184) have cited it from Vojvodina (Kumane; Stara Pazova).

***Ophonus (Ophonus) stictus* Stephens, 1828**

Material examined: “Fruška Gora Syrmien.”, 3 s. (MIZ).
Notes. First exact data for both Serbia and the Vojvodina Province. Species noted only from the Vojvodina Province without exact locality (ĆURČIĆ et al., 2007: 186).

***Parophonus (Parophonus) maculicornis* (Duftschmid, 1812)**

Material examined: “Fruska Gora”, 1 s. (MIZ); “Fruška Gora Syrmien.”, 1 s. (MIZ); “Jugoslavia Arandjelovac 20.VII-2.VIII '35 H. J. Mac Gillavry”, 1 s. (ZMAN).
Notes. Species cited for Vojvodina only from Kumane (ĆURČIĆ et al., 2007: 187).

***Trichotichnus (Trichotichnus) laevicollis* (Duftschmid, 1812)**

Material examined: “Fruska Gora”, 1 s. (MIZ).
Notes. New species for Serbia. Species was noted from the former Kosovo Province (ĆURČIĆ et al., 2007: 188). First mention of genus *Trichotichnus* Morawitz, 1863 from Serbia.

***Acupalpus (Acupalpus) meridianus* (Linnaeus, 1761)**

Material examined: "Fruska Gora", 53 s. (MIZ).

Notes. First exact record from the Vojvodina Province. Species was noted from Vojvodina without exact data (ĆURČIĆ et al., 2007: 189).

***Bradycellus (Bradycellus) distinctus* (Dejean, 1829)**

Material examined: "Fruska Gora", 1 s. (MIZ).

Notes. New species for Serbia. The right elytron of studied specimen has single minute pore on interval 3, which is abnormal character for *B. distinctus*.

***Stenolophus (Stenolophus) abdominalis* Gené, 1836**

Material examined: 27 s. labeled "Fruska Gora", "Fruska Gora Syrmien", and "Fruška Gora Syrmien." (MIZ).

Notes. MATITS (1922: 35, as *S. teutonius* var. *abdominalis*) has cited it for the country without exact data. First exact record for Serbia and first one for the Vojvodina Province. The Balkan populations of species refer to ssp. *persicus* Mannerheim, 1844.

***Stenolophus (Stenolophus) discophorus* (Fischer von Waldheim, 1823)**

Material examined: "Fruška Gora Syrmien.", 2 s. (MIZ).

Notes. Species known from Vojvodina only from Zrenjanin (ĆURČIĆ et al., 2007: 193).

***Stenolophus (Stenolophus) mixtus* (Herbst, 1784)**

Material examined: "Fruška Gora Syrmien.", 1 s. (MIZ).

Notes. ĆURČIĆ et al. (2007: 193) have cited for Vojvodina (Crvenka; Deliblato Sands).

***Cymindis (Cymindis) humeralis* (Geoffroy, 1785)**

Material examined: "Fruška Gora Syrmien.", 1 s. (MIZ).

Notes. First record from the Vojvodina Province.

***Cymindis (Cymindis) lineola* L. Dufour, 1820**

Material examined: "Jugoslavia Niš, 1957.IV" / "legit dr. Lenczy", 3 s. (HNHM).

Notes. New species for Serbia.

***Cymindis (Tarsostinus) macularis* Fischer von Waldheim, 1824**

Material examined: "Serbien Bor", 1 m. (MNHUB).

Notes. New species for Serbia. First data of *Tarsostinus* Motschulsky, 1864 from Serbia.

***Lebia (Lamprias) chlorocephala* (J.J. Hoffmann, 1803)**

Material examined: "Fruska Gora", 1 s. (MIZ); "Fruska Gora Syrmien", 1 s. (MIZ).

Notes. First record from the Vojvodina Province.

***Lebia (Lebia) cruxminor* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

Material examined: "Fruska Gora", 2 s. (MIZ).

Notes. ĆURČIĆ et al. (2007: 203) have indicated it for Vojvodina (Morović; Višnjićevo).

***Badister (Badister) meridionalis* Puel, 1925**

Material examined: "Jamena a. Save leg. Bischoff 1930", 1 s. (MNHUB); "Jugoslavia Arandjelovac 20.VII-2.VIII '35 H. J. Mac Gillavry", 4 s. (ZMAN).

Notes. New species for Serbia.

Badister (Badister) unipustulatus Bonelli, 1813

Material examined: 5 s. from localities “Fruska Gora” and “Fruška Gora Syrmien.” (MIZ).
Notes. First record from the Vojvodina Province.

Badister (Baudia) collaris Motschulsky, 1844

Material examined: 14 s. from localities “Fruska Gora”, “Fruska Gora Syrmien”, and “Fruška Gora Syrmien.” (MIZ; NMW).

Notes. First exact data for Serbia and first one from the Vojvodina Province. ĆURČIĆ et al. (2007: 208) have indicated it for the country without exact locality.

Badister (Baudia) peltatus (Panzer, 1796)

Material examined: “Fruška Gora Syrmien.”, 1 s. (MIZ); “Fruskagora Syrmien Paganetti”, 1 s. (NMW).

Notes. First exact record for both Serbia and the Vojvodina Province. So far, this species was noted only from Vojvodina without exact data (ĆURČIĆ et al., 2007: 208).

Badister (Trimorphus) sodalis (Duftschmid, 1812)

Material examined: “Jugoslavia Beograd 23.X.1960 W. Bazyuk leg.”, 1 m. (MIZ).

Notes. New species for Serbia. First report of *Trimorphus* Stephens, 1828 from Serbia.

Omphreus (Omphreus) bischoffi Meschnigg, 1934

Material examined: “Mokra Pl.” / “leg. Bischoff Montenegro 1933” / “*Omphreus bischoffi* n. m. type det. Ing. Meschnigg”, 1 f. **syntype** (MNHUB).

Oodes helopioides (Fabricius, 1792)

Material examined: “Fruska Gora”, 7 s. (MIZ); “Fruška Gora Syrmien.”, 5 s. (MIZ).

Notes. First record from the Vojvodina Province.

Panagaeus cruxmajor (Linnaeus, 1758)

Material examined: “Fruska Gora”, 8 s. (MIZ); “Fruška Gora Syrmien.”, 12 s. (MIZ).

Notes. ĆURČIĆ et al. (2007: 212) have cited it for Vojvodina (Morović; Višnjićevo).

Perigona (Trechicus) nigriceps (Dejean, 1831)

Material examined. “Jugoslavia Arandjelovac 20.VII-2.VIII '35 H. J. Mac Gillavry”, 4 s. (ZMAN).

Notes. New species for Serbia. First report also of the taxa *Perigonini* G.H. Horn, 1881, *Perigona* Laporte, 1835, and *Trechicus* LeConte, 1853 from Serbia.

Agonum (Agonum) sexpunctatum (Linnaeus, 1758)

Material examined: “Fruška Gora Syrmien.”, 7 s. (MIZ).

Notes. First record from the Vojvodina Province.

Agonum (Europhilus) micans (Nicolai, 1822)

Material examined: Around 90 s. from localities “Fruska Gora”, “Fruska Gora Syrmien”, and “Fruška Gora Syrmien.” (MIZ).

Notes. First record from the Vojvodina Province.

***Limodromus assimilis* (Paykull, 1790)**

Material examined: At least 150 s. from localities “Fruska Gora”, “Fruska Gora Syrmien”, and “Fruška Gora Syrmien.” (MIZ).

Notes. First record from the Vojvodina Province.

***Limodromus krynickii* (Sperk, 1835)**

Material examined: Around 90 s. from localities “Fruska Gora”, “Fruska Gora Syrmien”, and “Fruška Gora Syrmien.” (MIZ); “Jamena a. Save leg. Bischoff 1930”, 5 s. (MNHUB).

Notes. New species for Serbia.

***Limodromus longiventris* (Mannerheim, 1825)**

Material examined: “Fruska Gora”, 1 s. (MIZ); “Fruška Gora Syrmien.”, 6 s. (MIZ).

Notes. First record from the Vojvodina Province.

***Oxypselaphus obscurus* (Herbst, 1784)**

Material examined: 52 s. labelled “Fruska Gora”, “Fruska Gora Syrmien”, and “Fruška Gora Syrmien.” (MIZ).

Notes. First record from the Vojvodina Province.

***Platynus livens* (Gyllenhal, 1810)**

Material examined: 73 s. from localities “Fruska Gora”, “Fruska Gora Syrmien”, and “Fruška Gora Syrmien.” (MIZ).

Notes. First record from the Vojvodina Province.

***Platynus scrobiculatus* (Fabricius, 1801)**

Material examined: “Fruska Gora”, 17 s. (MIZ; NMW); “Fruska gora Syrmien Paganetti”, 2 s. (NMW); “Fruška Gora Syrmien.”, 60 s. (MIZ).

Notes. ĆURČIĆ et al. (2007: 221) have noted it from Fruška Gora Mt.

***Abax (Abacopercus) carinatus* (Duftschmid, 1812)**

Material examined: Around 50 s. labeled “Fruska Gora” and “Fruška Gora Syrmien.” (MIZ).

Notes. Species cited from the Fruška Gora Mt. (ĆURČIĆ et al., 2007: 224).

***Abax (Abax) parallelepipedus* (Piller & Mitterpacher, 1783)**

Material examined: “Fruska Gora Syrmien Paganetti”, 2 s. (NMW); more than 110 specimens from localities “Fruska Gora” and “Fruška Gora Syrmien.” (MIZ).

Notes. Species cited from the Fruška Gora Mt. (ĆURČIĆ et al., 2007: 225).

***Abax (Abax) parallelus* (Duftschmid, 1812)**

Material examined: “Fruška Gora Syrmien.”, 11 s. (MIZ).

Notes. Species cited from the Fruška Gora Mt. (ĆURČIĆ et al., 2007: 226).

***Molops (Molops) apfelbecki* Ganglbauer, 1891**

- *Molops apfelbecki pseudoalpestris* Mlynář, 1977

Material examined: “Jugoslavia: nr. Belgrade. vi.1938. Grebenchikoff. B.M. 1958-569”, 1 m. (BMNH).

- *Molops apfelbecki reiseri* Apfelbeck, 1904

Material examined: "Reiser 1899 Kopaonik" / "Coll. Apfelbeck", **lectotype** and 2 **paralectotypes** of *Molops reiseri* Apfelbeck, 1904 (HNHM); "Reiser 1899 Kopaonik", 1 m., 1 f. (MNHUB); "Yugoslavia: Kopaonik Mts., Subo Rudiste. 1800-2100m. 23-25.v.1936." / "V. & E. Martino. B.M.1938-733", 1 m., 1 f. (BMNH).

***Molops (Molops) elatus* (Fabricius, 1801)**

Material examined: "Fruska Gora", 1 m., 1 f. (MIZ); "Fruška Gora Syrmien.", 1 m. (MIZ).

Notes. First record from the Vojvodina Province. The population from Fruška Gora belongs to ssp. *plitvicensis* (Heyden, 1880).

***Molops (Molops) piceus* (Panzer, 1793)**

Material examined: "Fruska Gora", 1 s. (MIZ); "Fruška Gora Syrmien.", 2 s. (MIZ); "Serbia: Lipovica-Avala, 18 km S. of Belgrad. 20-22.iv.1936." / "V. Martino. B.M.1938-461.", 1 m. (BMNH).

Notes. Species cited from Avala and Fruška Gora (ĆURČIĆ et al., 2007: 232).

***Molops (Molops) rufipes* Chaudoir, 1843**

Material examined: "Yugoslavia: Kopaonik. 1600-1800m. 21.v.1936. K.Martino" / "V. & E. Martino. B.M.1938-733", 1 m. (BMNH).

***Poecilus (Poecilus) striatopunctatus* (Duftschmid, 1812)**

Material examined: "Serbia: Makis nr. Beograd. 29.iv.1936." / "E. Martino. B.M.1938-461", 2 s. (BMNH).

***Pterostichus (Argutor) cursor* (Dejean, 1828)**

Material examined: "Fruska Gora", 7 s. (MIZ); "Fruška Gora Syrmien.", 8 s. (MIZ).

Notes. First exact data for Serbia and first record from the Vojvodina Province. So far, it was noted for the country without exact locality (ĆURČIĆ et al., 2007: 243).

***Pterostichus (Argutor) vernalis* (Panzer, 1796)**

Material examined: "Fruska Gora", 3 s. (MIZ); "Fruška Gora Syrmien.", 4 s. (MIZ).

Notes. First exact record from the Vojvodina Province. Species was noted for Vojvodina without exact locality before (ĆURČIĆ et al., 2007: 244).

***Pterostichus (Bothriopterus) oblongopunctatus* (Fabricius, 1787)**

Material examined. "Fruska Gora", 1 s. (MIZ).

Notes. First record from the Vojvodina Province.

***Pterostichus (Cheporus) burmeisteri* Heer, 1838**

Material examined. "Fruska Gora", 5 s. (MIZ); "Fruška Gora Syrmien.", 6 s. (MIZ).

Notes. First record from the Vojvodina Province.

***Pterostichus (Cophosus) cylindricus* (Herbst, 1784)**

Material examined. "Fruska Gora", 5 s. (MIZ); "Fruška Gora Syrmien.", 2 s. (MIZ).

Notes. Species cited from the Fruška Gora Mt. (ĆURČIĆ et al., 2007: 246).

***Pterostichus (Feronidius) hungaricus* (Dejean, 1828)**

Material examined. "Fruska Gora", 6 s. (MIZ); "Fruška Gora Syrmien.", 9 s. (MIZ).

Notes. First record from the Vojvodina Province. It is worth mentioning that three related species, *P. hungaricus*, *P. incommodus* and *P. melas* s.l. inhabit Fruška Gora.

***Pterostichus (Feronidius) incommodus* Schaum, 1858**

Material examined. "Serbien Paracin 1918 Dr. Maertens", 2 s. (MNHUB); "Jugoslavia Nis, 1957 III." / "legit dr. Lenczy", 18 s. (HNHM); "Jugoslavia Nis, 1957 IV." / "legit dr. Lenczy", 17 s. (HNHM); "Fruška Gora Syrmien.", 1 m. (MIZ).

Notes. New species for Serbia. Species was recently recorded for the former Kosovo Province (CSIKI, 1940: 216; ĆURČIĆ et al., 2007: 247).

***Pterostichus (Feronidius) melas* (Creutzer, 1799)**

- *Pterostichus melas melas* (Creutzer, 1799)

Material examined: "Fruska Gora", 32 s. (MIZ); "Fruška Gora Syrmien.", 48 s. (MIZ); "Yugoslavia Beograd, Topcider. 20-21.iii.1936 V. & E. Martino. B.M.1938-733", 1 m. (BMNH).

- *Pterostichus melas depressus* (Dejean, 1828)

Material examined. "Jugoslavia Nis, 1957 IV." / "legit dr. Lenczy", 2 s. (HNHM); "Jugoslavia Nis, 1957 V." / "legit dr. Lenczy", 2 s. (HNHM).

***Pterostichus (Melanius) aterrimus* (Herbst, 1784)**

Material examined. "Fruška Gora Syrmien.", 1 s. (MIZ).

Notes. New species for Serbia.

***Pterostichus (Melanius) elongatus* (Duftschmid, 1812)**

Material examined. "Fruska Gora", 1 s. (MIZ).

Notes. First record from the Vojvodina Province.

***Pterostichus (Oreophilus) jurinei* (Panzer, 1803)**

Material examined: "Fruska Gora", 1 f. (MIZ); "Fruška Gora Syrmien.", 3 m., 6 f. (MIZ).

Notes. New species for Serbia. First report of *Oreophilus* Chaudoir, 1838 from Serbia.

***Pterostichus (Oreophilus) variolatus* (Dejean, 1828)**

Material examined: "dép. d'Užice Murtenica Planina Serbie occidentale" / "juin 1923 R. Jeannel, A. Magdelaine et A. Winkler", 2 s. (NMW).

Notes. New species for Serbia. The series from Murtenica Mt. is referred to ssp. *carniolicus* Ganglbauer, 1891.

***Pterostichus (Parahaptoderus) brevis* (Duftschmid, 1812)**

Material examined: "Yugoslavia: Kopaonik Mts., Subo Rudiste. 1800-2100m. 23-25.v.1936." / "V. & E. Martino. B.M.1938-733", 1 s (BMNH).

Notes. Species already recorded from the Kopaonik Mt. (ĆURČIĆ et al., 2007: 251).

***Pterostichus (Phonias) strenuus* (Panzer, 1796)**

Material examined. "Fruška Gora Syrmien.", 1 s. (MIZ).

Notes. First exact record from the Vojvodina Province. Species was noted from Vojvodina without exact data (ĆURČIĆ et al., 2007: 252).

***Pterostichus (Pseudomaseus) gracilis* (Dejean, 1828)**

Material examined: “Fruska Gora”, 1 s. (NMW).

Notes. First exact data from the Vojvodina Province. Species was cited for Vojvodina without exact data (ĆURČIĆ et al., 2007: 255).

***Pterostichus (Pseudomaseus) anthracinus* (Illiger, 1798)**

Material examined. SERBIA. “Jugoslavia Arandjelovac 20.VII-2.VIII '35 H. J. Mac Gilavry”, 2 s. (ZMAN).

***Pterostichus (Pseudosteropus) illigeri* (Panzer, 1803)**

Material examined: “Fruska Gora”, 1 s. (MIZ); “Fruška Gora Sarmien”, 1 s. (MIZ).

Notes. New species for Serbia. First report of *Pseudosteropus* Chaudoir, 1838 from Serbia. Apart from the first and second specimens properly labeled from Fruška Gora, I have found 15 more specimens, which most probably come from the same locality.

***Pterostichus (Pterostichus) brucki* Schaum, 1859**

Material examined: “dép. d'Užice Murtenica Planina Serbie occidentale” / “juin 1923 R. Jeannel, A. Magdelaine et A. Winkler”, 5 s. (MNHN).

***Pterostichus (Pterostichus) fasciatopunctatus* (Creutzer, 1799)**

Material examined: “Fruska Gora”, 1 s. (MIZ); “Fruška Gora Sarmien.”, 9 s. (MIZ).

Notes. Second data for Serbia and first one for the Vojvodina Province. This species was hitherto known only from the Lim River Valley (ĆURČIĆ et al., 2007: 256).

***Platyderus (Platyderus) rufus* (Duftschmid, 1812)**

Material examined: “Yugoslavia Beograd, Topcider. 20-21.iii.1936 V. & E. Martino. B.M.1938-733”, 1 m. (BMNH).

***Laemostenus (Laemostenus) venustus* (Dejean, 1828)**

Material examined: “Fruska Gora”, 1 s. (NMW).

Notes. First exact record for Serbia and first one from the Vojvodina Province. ĆURČIĆ et al. (2007: 268) have indicated it for the country without exact locality.

***Laemostenus (Pristonychus) punctatus* (Dejean, 1828)**

Material examined: “Fruška Gora Sarmien.”, 4 s. (MIZ); “Tschatschak Serbie”, 1 s. (NMW).

Notes. Species cited for Fruška Gora (ĆURČIĆ et al., 2007: 269, as *L. terricola* (Herbst, 1784)).

***Amara (Amara) anthobia* A. Villa & G.B. Villa, 1833**

Material examined: “Fruška Gora Sarmien.”, 2 s. (MIZ).

Notes. First exact record from the Vojvodina Province. Species was noted for Vojvodina without exact data (ĆURČIĆ et al., 2007: 272).

***Amara (Amara) curta* Dejean, 1828**

Material examined: “Fruska Gora”, 1 s. (MIZ).

Notes. First record from the Vojvodina Province.

***Amara (Amara) lunicollis* Schiödte, 1837**

Material examined: "Fruska Gora", 1 s. (MIZ).

Notes. Species cited only from Kruševac (ĆURČIĆ et al., 2007: 276). Second record from Serbia and first one from the Vojvodina Province.

***Amara (Amara) montivaga* Sturm, 1825**

Material examined: "Fruska Gora Sirmien", 1 s. (MIZ).

Notes. Species cited for the Fruška Gora Mt. (ĆURČIĆ et al., 2007: 276).

***Amara (Amara) nitida* Sturm, 1825**

Material examined: "Fruska Gora", 1 s. (MIZ).

Notes. First exact record from the Vojvodina Province. Hitherto this species was noted for Vojvodina without exact data (ĆURČIĆ et al., 2007: 277).

***Amara (Amara) ovata* (Fabricius, 1792)**

Material examined: "Fruška Gora Sirmien.", 6 s. (MIZ).

Notes. First exact record from the Vojvodina Province.

***Amara (Amarocelia) erratica* (Duftschmid, 1812)**

Material examined: "Serb. Kopaonik Suvo Rudište VII.10, Rambousek", 1 s. (MNHUB).

Notes. Species recorded from Fruška Gora Mt. (ĆURČIĆ et al., 2007: 282).

***Amara (Bradytus) fulva* (O.F. Müller, 1776)**

Material examined: "Fruska Gora", 6 s. (MIZ); "Fruška Gora Sirmien.", 2 s. (MIZ).

Notes. ĆURČIĆ et al. (2007: 281) have cited it for Vojvodina (Deliblato Sands; Dolovo).

***Amara (Curtonotus) aulica* (Panzer, 1796)**

Material examined: "Fruska Gora", 1 s. (MIZ); "Fruška Gora Sirmien.", 2 s. (MIZ).

Notes. ĆURČIĆ et al. (2007: 281) have cited it for the Vojvodina Province (Kumane).

***Amara (Paracelia) quenseli* (Schönherr, 1806)**

Material examined: "Kopaonik Serb. 27.8.24", 1 s. (MNHUB).

Notes. Species noted from the Kopaonik Mt. (ĆURČIĆ et al., 2007: 285).

***Amara (Paracelia) serdicana* Apfelbeck, 1904**

Material examined: "Serb. Hlf. Niš", 1 s. (MNHUB).

Notes. First exact record from the country.

***Amara (Xenocelia) ingenua* (Duftschmid, 1812)**

Material examined: "Fruska Gora", 1 s. (MIZ).

Notes. ĆURČIĆ et al. (2007: 283) have listed it for the Vojvodina Province.

***Zabrus (Pelor) rhodopensis* Apfelbeck, 1904**

Material examined: "Mazedonien Moravatal 3.9.1934 Zwick S.", 1 s. (MNHUB).

Notes. Species cited with exact record only from Surdulica (ĆURČIĆ et al., 2007: 290, as *Z. balcanicus rhodopensis*).

***Zabrus (Pelor) incrassatus* (Ahrens, 1814)**

Material examined: “Mazedonien Moravatal 3.9.1934 Zwick S.”, 1 s. (MNHUB).

Notes. Species known only from South Serbia (ĆURČIĆ et al., 2007: 290).

***Zabrus (Zabrus) tenebrioides* (Goeze, 1777)**

Material examined: “Fruška Gora”, 2 s. (MIZ).

Notes. ĆURČIĆ et al. (2007: 292) have cited it for the Vojvodina Province.

***Polystichus connexus* (Geoffroy, 1785)**

Material examined: “Fruška Gora Syrmien.”, 6 s. (MIZ).

Notes. Species noted for Vojvodina without exact data (ĆURČIĆ et al., 2007: 293). First exact record from the Vojvodina Province.

Conclusion

This paper reports 157 species from Serbia. Twenty species, e.g. *Bembidion concoeruleum*, *Tachyura diabrachys*, *Trechus constrictus*, *T. limacodes*, *T. rotundipennis*, *Harpalus taciturnus*, *Ophonus brevicollis*, *Trichotichnus laevicollis*, *Bradycellus distinctus*, *Cymindis lineola*, *C. macularis*, *Badister meridionalis*, *B. sodalis*, *Perigona nigriceps*, *Limodromus krynickii*, *Pterostichus incommodus*, *P. aterrimus*, *P. jurinei*, *P. variolatus*, and *P. illigeri*, are first reported from Serbia. The tribe Perigonini, the genera *Perigona* and *Trichotichnus* as well as the subgenera *Tarsostinus*, *Trimorphus*, *Trechicus*, *Oreophilus*, and *Pseudosteropus* are also first reported for the country. Nine species, e.g. *Harpalus caspius*, *Ophonus puncticeps*, *O. stictus*, *Stenolophus abdominalis*, *Badister collaris*, *B. peltatus*, *Pterostichus cursor*, *Laemostenus venustus*, and *Amara serdicana*, are first reported for Serbia with exact data/localities. Other seven species (*Sinechostictus doderoi*, *Chlaenius olivieri*, *Harpalus tenebrosus*, *H. servus*, *H. subcylindricus*, *Pterostichus fasciatopunctatus*, and *Amara lunicollis*) are confirmed for the fauna, being noted for second time from Serbia. Finally, 111 species are recorded from the Vojvodina Province, as 108 of them come from the Fruška Gora Mt. 56 species are first cited for the Vojvodina Province, and 13 more are first recorded for it with exact data.

Notes on the forest carabid fauna of Fruška Gora Mt.

Fruška Gora is often treated as the northern- and easternmost branch of the Dinaric Mts. (CVETIĆ, SABOVLJEVIĆ, 2005). Based on an analysis of the ranges of 15 typical forest species (from *Leistus* Frölich, *Aptinus* Bonelli, *Trechus* Clairville, *Abax* Bonelli, *Molops* Bonelli, *Cheporus* Latreille, *Oreophilus* Chaudoir, *Pseudosteropus* Chaudoir, and *Pterostichus* Bonelli s.str.), we may conclude that Fruška Gora has played the role of a forest “island” in the South Pannonian Plane and acts as a refuge of East Alpine – West Dinaric forest fauna. The analysis shows that fourteen of the investigated species inhabit the Eastern Alps and the westernmost area of the Balkans but not the main area of the Balkan Peninsula. Most of these species are also distributed more or less widely in Central Europe from France to West Ukraine. This inference is similar to that of SÓLYMOS et al. (2004) that the forest snail fauna of Fruška Gora is composed of general Central European species.

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Нови данни за бръмбарите-бегачи (Coleoptera: Carabidae) на Сърбия

Борислав ГЕОРГИЕВ

(Резюме)

В колекциите на седем европейски музеи са установени 1887 екземпляра от 157 вида от семейство Carabidae от Сърбия. Двадесет вида, 5 подрода, 2 рода и 1 трибус са нови за фауната на страната, 9 вида са публикувани за първи път с точни находища, а други 7 вида – за втори път за страната. Общо 111 вида са съобщени за автономната провинция Войводина, като 56 вида са нови за нейната фауна, а други 13 са съобщени за нея за първи път с точни находки.